

February 2023

Press Release

Ten European projects join forces to protect the complex ICT infrastructures and create a stronger, more innovative and resilient European industry.

In an increasingly connected world, the Internet of Things (IoT) brings new value and business benefits to people worldwide. At the heart of all this is the data being generated and exchanged, providing new insights into better ways of working and living.

To take full advantage of these innovative improvements, there is also a need to address the challenges that emerge. For instance, there is a need to make sure that connected objects and the data they generate are only accessible to authorized people and machines. Implementing IoT solutions effectively means deploying them securely.

With the aim of creating a more cyber-secure Europe, the European Commission selected several projects that directly address the cybersecurity needs of the EU industry and society. Each project has concrete applications which focus on different verticals/application domains: education, energy, healthcare, manufacturing mobility, 5G and 6G networks, emergency and vigilance or smart cities. Those solutions have joined forces and organized a workshop with cybersecurity at the heart of the discussion.

The EU-made cybersecurity workshop is designed to provide attendees with the knowledge to create safe, resilient, and trustworthy applications and services. The online workshop will cover a range of topics related to cybersecurity.

The workshop, which has been jointly organised by [ARCADIAN-IoT](#), [ELECTRON](#), [ERATOSTHENES](#), [IDUNN](#), [IRIS](#), [KRAKEN](#), [SECANT](#), [SENTINEL](#), [SPATIAL](#), [TRUST aWARE](#) projects, will provide an overview of how novel solutions can protect the complex ICT

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement N° 101021808.

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There are many topics to be addressed:

- Best practices for designing and building secure applications and services.
- Techniques for identifying and mitigating cybersecurity risks.
- Strategies for ensuring the resilience of applications and services in the face of cyber threats.

The EU-funded [SPATIAL project](#) is working towards a trustworthy governance and regulatory framework for AI-driven security in Europe. The topic that will be addressed is 5G/6G and it will be presented by [Madhusanka Liyanage](#), Assistant Professor/ Ad Astra Fellow at the [University College of Dublin](#).

Check the agenda and register at this [link](#).

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